

(50.0 ml) and constant ionic strength (0.1M NaClO₄) were titrated against standard alkali at a temperature 30°±0.1°. The pK_a value of the ligand, 3.85, as reported by Khadikar⁵ under the same experimental conditions was used for the calculation of formation constant of In(III)-lactate complexes.

In calculating $\bar{n}$ and $p^{[4-1]}$ the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for $\bar{n}$ and $p^{[4-1]}$ corresponding to different values of pH were calculated and formation curve obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ values against $p^{[4-1]}$ (Fig. 2). From the formation curve the approximate values of log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ were obtained from half-integral values of $\bar{n}$ and their refinement was made by the method of least squares as well as by point-wise calculations (Table 1). The standard deviation of the values of log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ are found to be ±0.03, ±0.03 and ±0.05 respectively.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF IN(III)-LACTATES

	Bjerrum's method	Point-wise calculation	Least square method
Log K ₁	2.60	2.58	2.62
Log K ₂	1.44	1.47	1.45
Log K ₃	0.72	0.72	0.76
log β ₂	4.04	4.05	4.07
log β ₃	4.76	4.77	4.83

The 1:3 complex was isolated as described by Khadikar *et al.*⁶. The I.R. spectrum of the 1:3 complex having the composition InL₃.3H₂O (In Obs. 26.40%, Cal. 26.34%) and that of lactic acid was

Fig. 2. Formation Curve In(III)-Lactate.

obtained by KBr disc technique. Based on the bidentate nature of the ligand octahedral stereochemistry may be assigned to the complex. It seems, therefore, that the water molecules present in the complex are not co-ordinated and are in the second co-ordination sphere. Considerable shift in the hydroxyl group frequency from 3500 cm⁻¹ in lactic acid to 3300 cm⁻¹ in the complex was observed. The ionised carboxyl group stretching frequency is also found to have been shifted to 1590 cm⁻¹ (ligand 1750 cm⁻¹). This suggests that the chelation has taken place involving co-ordination of both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups of the lactate ion. The presence of water molecules could not be confirmed by the I.R. spectrum of the complex since medium absorption bands of γ(OH) in the range 3480-3400 cm⁻¹ and of δ(HOH) in the range 1640-1630 cm⁻¹ overlaps with the hydroxyl and carboxyl group frequencies of In(III)-lactate. However, a weak band at 765 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the presence of water in the complex in accordance with Nakamoto⁷.

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Molecular Adducts of Diaryltin dihalides with Formamide and its Substituted Derivatives

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IN continuation to our studies on the acceptor property of diaryltin dihalides¹⁻⁶, we now describe synthesis and characterisation of some new molecular adducts of diaryltin dihalides with formamide (F) and its substituted derivatives viz., N-methylformamide (NMF), diethyl formamide (DEF) and

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NOTES

TABLE I—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR ADDUCTS AND DIARYLTIN DIHALIDES

Complex	m.p. °C	Analysis (%) Found (Calcd.)				Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	Mol. Cond. mho-cm ⁻² / mole
		C	H	N	Sn		
1. *Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .4F	82	36.1 (36.6)	4.3 (4.2)	10.2 (10.6)	23.6 (22.7)		
2. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2F	110—112	37.2 (38.7)	3.4 (3.7)	6.0 (6.4)	26.8 (27.4)		1.22
3. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .2F	78—80	31.0 (32.1)	3.4 (3.0)	5.3 (5.3)	22.2 (22.7)		
4. (<i>m</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .2F	84—85	40.9 (41.5)	3.9 (4.3)	6.2 (6.0)	26.1 (25.7)		
5. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .2F	96—98	41.1 (41.5)	4.1 (4.3)	6.1 (6.0)	25.3 (25.7)		
6. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnBr ₂ .2F	123—125	34.9 (34.8)	3.8 (3.6)	5.4 (5.0)	21.4 (21.6)		
7. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2NMF	112	41.8 (41.5)	4.5 (4.3)	5.9 (6.0)	26.2 (25.7)	294 (462)	0.88
8. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .2NMF	65—66	34.6 (34.8)	3.5 (3.6)	5.2 (5.1)	21.6 (21.5)		
9. Ph ₂ SnI ₂ .2NMF	79—82	29.7 (29.7)	3.0 (3.1)	4.8 (4.3)	17.7 (18.5)		
10. (<i>o</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .2NMF	95—97	44.6 (44.1)	4.6 (4.9)	5.6 (5.7)	24.6 (24.2)	297 (490)	
11. (<i>o</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnBr ₂ .2NMF	77—80	37.5 (37.3)	4.2 (4.1)	4.3 (4.8)	20.4 (4.8)	(20.5)	
12. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .2NMF	69—71	45.2 (44.1)	5.1 (4.9)	5.5 (5.7)	23.9 (24.2)	276 (490)	
13. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnBr ₂ .2NMF	61—64	37.2 (37.3)	4.3 (4.1)	4.4 (4.8)	20.0 (20.5)		
14. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2DEF	59—61	48.4 (48.4)	6.1 (5.9)	5.4 (5.1)	21.2 (21.7)	302 (546)	0.63
15. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .DEF	55—56	46.1 (45.8)	4.8 (4.7)	3.0 (3.1)	26.6 (26.7)	260 (445)	
16. (<i>o</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DEF	77—78	48.4 (48.2)	5.1 (5.3)	3.2 (2.9)	25.3 (25.2)	283 (473)	
17. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DEF	100—102	48.3 (48.2)	5.4 (5.3)	2.7 (2.9)	26.0 (25.2)	295 (473)	
18. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnBr ₂ .DEF	74—76	40.4 (40.5)	4.6 (4.5)	2.6 (2.4)	21.9 (21.2)		
19. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .DPF	74—75	56.1 (55.5)	4.4 (3.9)	2.5 (2.6)	22.7 (21.9)	320 (541)	0.46
20. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .DPF	56—57	47.8 (47.6)	3.5 (3.3)	2.5 (2.2)	18.1 (18.8)		
21. (<i>o</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DPF	93—95	56.5 (56.9)	4.5 (4.4)	2.3 (2.5)	20.2 (20.9)	295 (569)	
22. (<i>p</i> -tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DPF	84—85	57.2 (56.9)	4.3 (4.4)	2.8 (2.5)	20.3 (20.9)	302 (569)	

* Ph = phenyl.

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) OF LEWIS BASES AND THEIR ADDUCTS WITH DIARYLTIN DIHALIDES*

Compound**	$\sqrt{C=O}$	$\sqrt{C-N}$ contiguous to C=O	$\sqrt{N-C}$ contiguous to CH ₃	$\delta O = C-N$	$\sqrt{Sn-O}$	$\sqrt{Sn-Cl}$	$\sqrt{Sn-Ph}$	
							asym	sym
F	1678 vs	1313 vs	—	600 vs(br)	—	—	—	—
1	1675 sh 1660 s	1320 s 1372 s	—	626 s	348 w	278 m	282 m	235 m
2	1668 vs	1368 vs	—	630 s	344 w	270 s	280 m	230 p
3	1666 vs	1367 vs	—	627 vs	351 w	—	285 m	231 w
4	1667 vs	1370 s	—	627 s	350 w	276 m	286 m	238 w
5	1665 vs	1370 s	—	622 s	348 w	280 m	290 m	242 m
6	1660 vs	1369 s	—	629 s	346 w	—	287 m	243 w
NMF	1670 vs	1255 s	1155 s	663 s	—	—	—	—
7	1648 vs	1267 s	1164 s	***	355 s	260 m	285 m	230 w
8	1647 vs	1266 s	1164 s		355 m	—	280 m(br)	231 w
9	1644 vs	1264 vs	1159 s		355 m	—	270 m	238 m
10	1644 vs	1268 m	1163 m		335 m	264 m	285 w	250 w
11	1644 vs	1267 s	1160 m		333 m	—	282 w	253 w
12	1645 vs	1265 s	1158 m		335 m	264 m	274 m	248 m
13	1645 vs	1265 s	1160 m		338 m	—	267 m	248 m
DEF	1666 vs	1258 s	1116 s	636 s	—	—	—	—
14	1635 vs	1268 s	1133 s	649 s	348 m	274 m	287 m	248 m
15	1637 vs	1270 m	1135 w	646 s	342 m	272 m	290 m	250 m
16	1627 vs	1264 m	1125 w	—	347 m	279 m	287 m	248 m
17	1633 vs	1264 m	1123 w	648 s	349 m	276 m	289 m	251 m
18	1627 vs	1265 m	1128 w	650 s	351 m	—	291 m	247 w
DFP	1685 vs	1262 s	1142 m	616 w	—	—	—	—
19	1630 vs	1273 s	1167 m	630 sh	337 m	281 m	290 m	251 m
20	1628 vs	1272 s	1165 m	628 sh	341 m	—	288 m	249 m
21	1630 vs	1274 s	1170 m	636 w	340 m	278 m	287 m	248 w
22	1625 vs	1270 s	1166 m	632 w	343 m	277 m	283 m	246 m

* Spectra recorded in Nujol

** Serial numbers refer to complexes in Table 1.

*** Masked by strong ring vibrations.

diphenyl formamide (DPF). The infrared spectral data have been employed to suggest possible structure of the adducts.

Experimental

The Lewis acids were prepared by standard methods⁷ and the bases from Eastman Organics were used after distillation under reduced pressure. The method of preparation of the complexes was essentially the same as reported for the corresponding $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2DMF$ adducts⁶. Molecular weight of some typical complexes was determined cryscopically in benzene and the molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solution of a few representative adducts was measured at 30° using Phillips conductivity assembly PR-9500. The infrared spectra of the Lewis bases and their complexes in Nujol were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 521 in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

The experimental data on the newly prepared co-ordination compounds are given in the Table 1. Most of the complexes possess 1 : 2 stoichiometry with a hexa co-ordinated tin atom. However, DEF and DPF yield 1 : 1 adducts presumably due to large size of the Lewis bases which hinders the increase of co-ordination number greater than five. F yields a product $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2 \cdot 4F$, in which the two additional molecules of the base are apparently attached through hydrogen bonding as shown by its infrared spectra.

The complexes are crystalline solids, soluble in common organic solvents, thermally stable and slightly hygroscopic. Abnormally low values for molecular weight indicate significant dissociation of the complexes in solution and their molar conductance data show absence of ionic species. The reaction of these complexes with some stronger donors such as 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, dimethyl sulphoxide and pyridine N-oxide resulted in complete displacement of the amide molecules indicating their comparatively weak donor ability. The relevant infrared absorption frequencies are given in Table 2.

A comparison of the absorptions due to $\sqrt{C} = O$, $\sqrt{C-N}$, $\sqrt{N-C}$ and $\delta O = C-N$ in free Lewis bases with those in their complexes indicate co-ordination from the oxygen atom of the ligands which is confirmed by identification of an absorption due to $\sqrt{Sn-O}$ at $345 \pm 10 cm^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the complexes but absent in those of the free bases. The results are in agreement with those reported by previous workers on the complexes of formamide and its substituted derivatives with metal halides^{6,8}.

$\sqrt{asym^{sn-cl}}$ and $\sqrt{symm^{sn-cl}}$ occurs at 365 and 356 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectrum of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2$. The spectra of its complexes show only one

$Sn-Cl$ stretching vibration at $270 \pm 10 cm^{-1}$ showing a negative shift of about 80 cm^{-1} , characteristic of the increase in the co-ordination number of the tin atom^{9,10}. The corresponding $Sn-Br$ and $Sn-I$ absorptions lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra. The absorption located at 277 ± 13 and $240 \pm 10 cm^{-1}$ are assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretchings of the $Sn-aryl$ bond respectively¹¹, and are not significantly changed from those in the parent Lewis acids.

In view of the presence of two $Sn-aryl$ and one $Sn-Cl$ stretching vibrations, the octahedry adducts of the formula $R_2SnCl_2 \cdot 2L$ may be suggested to have two aryl groups in the *cis* position and the two chlorine atoms *trans* to each other. Since the spectra of 1 : 1 complexes are not significantly different from those of 1 : 2 complexes, they are presumed to be penta co-ordinated with a trigonal bipyramidal geometry, likely to have two aryl groups and a ligand molecule in the equatorial position and the two chlorine atoms, *trans* to each other in the apical position.

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